

TF2 ENVRI AAAI - white paper

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1. Objectives

The overarching goal is to carry out implementation within the sub-domain RIs, with the support of WP7 for technical implementation on the basis of Architecture definition by TF2 in WP5.

Premise: ENVRI-FAIR is not aiming at building a centralized ENVRI-FAIR identity provider, which has implications in terms of sustainability and risk of using an external supplier balanced by saving of resources and wider compatibility;

Goal #1: negotiate among RIs a protocol that allows RIs to *federate* access to shared resources;

Goal #2: the above implies having an ENVRI-FAIR federation where users, once logged in (authenticated) can *access shared resources* (authentication);

Goal #3: Although there is an heterogeneous landscape in terms of permissions associated to resources and datasets from communities, TF2 is willing to tackle the authorisation issue, for instance by agreeing on a "*minimal level*" of *permissions* to access other ENV RIs (example: envri guest permissions) (authorisation);

Goal #4: once the AAAI federation is set up and tested within the ENVRI-FAIR cluster, this can be *extended to EOSC*;

Goal #5: promote the elaboration and adoption of *authorisation policies* within the specific RIs, as part of data policy;

2. Work to date

- TF2 establishment in Dresden
- Regular calls
- Tutorial session with AARC2
 - Blueprint Architecture
- Landscaping exercise
 - first survey of involved RIs
 - Use cases and requirements
 - Agreed TF2 Statements
- The current White Paper

3. Architecture

AAAI has 3 As, Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting. In fact there should be an 'I' before the first 'A' for Identification. However, for our purposes, Identification is implied by Authentication. At some point accounting may become necessary in order to achieve equitability of resource usage across interoperating RIs (and with EOSC and other external organisations). However, for this paper we concentrate on Authentication and Authorisation.

The Blueprint Architecture (BPA) by AARC2 provides a meaningful starting point and is recommended as a reference for setting up individual RIs' AAI systems and for creating the ENVRI-FAIR federation.

4. Implications

The above listed goals together with the BPA by AARC2 have some implications that should be considered in order to properly advise RIs and for carrying out the technical work.

Technical

Implication #1: need for a reference implementation (robust and working);

Implication #2: we need an underlying process and logic to manage Authorisations and restrictions (e.g. SLA based on Constraint programming);

Implication #3: need to converge towards an agreed key technology for federating RIs, e.g. OAuth2 (there can be others);

Implication #4: need for tight communication channels among RIs' AAI managers, and definition of procedures;

Implication #5: Need a contact list of AAI system managers at each ENVRI RI to (a) ensure architectural compatibility implementation (essentially interface and mechanisms of passing tokens); (b) mechanisms for interoperating backed up by a 'reward system' to encourage implementation of mechanisms for interoperation.

Governance and legalistic

Implication #1: different governance bodies in RIs need to agree about what information can be shared. *A governance framework is needed.* EOSC is the context where it is likely to be set-up on a European scale but ENVRI should contribute. Of particular relevance is GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation <https://gdpr.eu/>).

5. Authentication

In this section we are detailing some of the critical aspects of Authentication that need to be considered while deciding a shared policy. The very concept of User Authentication is tightly knit to the one of User authorisation and is deemed to include Identification.

5.1. Overview

Like many other software technologies, user authentication can be seen as a stack made of different components that, when used all together, provide a service.

When speaking of authentication in a distributed environment, the current best practices highlight three principal solutions:

- **Single Sign On:** SSO is a solution wherein the user upon login, is redirected and is actually signing into an [Identity Provider](#) (IdP) which authenticates them and creates the active session. The actual application the user is trying to access, underneath, delegates authentication to the IdP, and so does any other application configured within the same SSO system. By doing this an application can verify a user's identity just by looking at their session information. These applications rely on a centralized IdP to authenticate the end user, emanate session tokens, and verify the authenticity of such tokens. A real life example of this solution is the Google services environment, where a user can switch between services such as GMail, Drive, Youtube, and AdWords without having to log into each one of them.
- **Federated Identity:** in a Federated Identity scenario users can log in to a system using another system's credentials. The underlying mechanism consists in connecting two or more Identity Providers together to create a chain of trust. It is often used when connecting two corporate systems together. A real life example of Identity Federation is logging in with a Google account or a facebook account to a Website. Identity Federation can be used to implement SSO, but Identity Federation does not imply SSO and SSO does not necessarily imply federation across different identity providers.
- **Delegated identity:** a system can delegate its identity management, which means outsourcing user authentication to a third party system. By adopting this solution all the user management issues and their related problems (except identification and authorisation) are pushed into the IdP. A real life example of Delegate Identity is using Facebook Connect to authenticate users within an application. Delegated Identity is used in SSO, but its usage does not necessarily imply SSO.

These three solutions are not exclusive, e.g. you can have a SSO with federated identity, and share some degree of overlap with each other in the sense that they are built around the same components. All of them rely, in fact, on an Identity Provider (IdP) that can be a standalone system, or part of a trust chain, integrated into another system, or disjointed, and can delegate single usage permissions, or tokens shared across multiple systems. In this sense SSO can be seen as a way of streamlining user experience, with identity federation and delegation being the mechanism that allows different systems to share the same pool of user accounts. It is however important to understand the key difference between identity federation and delegation.

A federated solution means that visitors can use any account they have, as long as it is compatible. It makes no difference to the application site which account is being used, as long as it can interoperate. On the other hand a delegated solution implies that visitors cannot use any other accounts except the ones offered by the vendors you have pre-selected.

Various authentication mechanisms are in use in ENVRI. However, there is a general movement towards a token-based authentication system using external IdP (Identity providers) and using software that enables integration across authenticated identities from multiple IdPs.

5.2. Federation Requirements

There exist a wealth of protocols to handle user identity federation, and each of these protocols has multiple implementations, both open and proprietary. Since the chosen implementation is transparent to us, we will focus on the available protocols and leave the choice of the implementation to adopt to each RI.

A common protocol shared across the ENVRI RIs should adhere to the following requirements:

1. **Be implemented in a variety of off the shelf solutions**, possibly including open source ones. The rationale of this requirement lies in the fact that ENVRI RIs are not software houses and cannot afford to design and maintain their own protocols and technologies.
2. **Be already widely adopted** within the Research domain and in other real world cases. The rationale of this requirement is that adopting an already broadly used solution will put ENVRI RIs in the condition of federating their IdPs with a broad number of subjects without the need to manage proxies.
3. **Be supported by its regulating body**. Some solutions, though being still widely used, are considered by their designers and maintainers as surpassed due to architectural limits or security flaws. Since we expect ENVRI identities to withstand the test of time, or at least the test of IT times, we shall exclude a priori protocols that are flagged as obsolete, deprecated, or prone to well known leaks and attacks.
4. **Be compatible with state of the art technologies** like microservices, RESTful APIs, and cloud environments in general, ENVRI acknowledges that the trend of migrating services towards distributed cloud infrastructures is increasingly relevant and AAI technologies should not hinder such a process.
5. **Be used seamlessly by humans and applications**: in the context of big science it is more important than ever to facilitate researchers in crafting their own tools and allowing them to automate complex workflows based on data and services provided by third parties is therefore an important requirement. ENVRI realises that also applications should be able to authenticate into its services just as much as humans do and without the need for human intervention in the process.
6. **Be able to handle authorisation**: identification and authorisation are tightly linked to each other and although not all RIs have defined their policies on user authorisations, the adopted protocol should be able to manage them, thus securing access to APIs and other online resources;

These requirements are motivated by the principle that ENVRI RIs, at their core, are research organizations and have limited resources to invest on IT development, so developing a new protocol is not feasible and adopting as reference protocol something that

may become demanding in terms of management effort may deter several RIs from complying with it.

We are briefly presenting the most well known User Identity Federation protocols

- **SAML1.1:** SAML is an xml standard to exchange authentication and authorisation information across different domains designed and maintained by the Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards. It was designed with SSO as the main use case and for several years it has been the reference solution for most enterprise applications. Nowadays SAML 1.1 is used mostly in legacy systems and OASIS recommends to adopt its successor, SAML2.
- **SAML2:** an evolution of the SAML standard, it represents the convergence of different protocols that emerged in the early 2000s. SAML2 is nowadays the reference solution for most enterprise applications. It is incompatible with its 1.1 sibling and requires consistently human intervention to access services and resources, so it is unadvised to manage with it automated workflows where APIs require authorisation.
- **WS-Federation:** Web Service Federation is an Identity Federation specification built as an extension to SOAP. Part of the larger [Web Services Security](#) framework, WS-Federation defines mechanisms for allowing different security realms to broker information on identities, identity attributes and authentication.
- **OAuth2:** OAuth is primarily an authorisation protocol, meant to grant access to services in a distributed environment, however, it can be used to handle identification too or, to be more precise, pseudo-identification, i.e. a shallow identification paradigm wherein users are identified by their permissions rather than their personal data. OAuth is widely used in a large number of commercial and open source applications and it is the backbone of services such as Google Accounts.
- **OpenID Connect:** OpenID Connect 1.0 is an identity layer on top of the OAuth 2.0 protocol. It is supported by several major companies and allows for a REST-like communication between client applications and IdPs.
- **WS-Trust:** Like WS-Federation, WS-Trust is part of the WS framework and it is meant to deal with the issuing, renewing, and validating of security tokens. It is primarily meant for SOAP services and it is hence not compatible with REST services.

Aside from these well known protocols, there exists a wealth of other solutions, however they are not as ubiquitous as the above mentioned protocols are.

We can easily draw a compatibility matrix between the presented protocols and the ENVRI requirements.

Table I. Compatibility Matrix: Protocols vs Requirements

	1	2	3	4	5	6
SAML 1.1	Green	Green	Red	Red	Green	Green
SAML 2.0	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
WS-Federation	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green
OAUTH 2	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Open ID connect	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
WS-Trust	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green

We can easily identify OpenID Connect and OAuth-based pseudo-identification as the solutions that appear to comply with all of the ENVRI requirements.

The adoption of one of these protocols however does not exclude the other ones since proxying is always possible and most off the shelf solutions come with support for different protocols.

5.3. Proposal

RIs within the Task Force 2 group are open to use or be interoperable with OAuth2 (+ OpenID).

5.4. Recommended Technologies

A review of the potential technologies to be adopted to fulfill the requirements, compatible with the architecture and with the suggested protocols, was done. TF2 is not endorsing any specific technology or vendor, however the group considers it useful to know what and how many technologies can be considered to implement AAI.

The full list is in Annex III.

The white paper is not endorsing any specific solutions but just emphasizing that solutions already exist that implement requirements at a different.

In order to facilitate implementation, the writing group also suggest to consult the Certified OpenID Connect Implementations at this weblink <https://openid.net/developers/certified/> and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SAML-based_products_and_services

5.5. Authorisation

Authorisation is an ongoing challenge. There is detailed work within EPOS to characterise the authorisations used currently in the subdomains of EPOS.

The problem is that different organizations have different authorisation schemas, thus finding a common ground is far from being a trivial problem.

A landscape analysis is inevitable and is made hard by the fact that in most organizations' authorisation policies are implicit and the API calls (implementing those policies) can be observed on servers.

Authorization may be defined as the availability of the asset for use by whom (individual or group), in what role, over what time period, with what permissions (CRUDEL: Create, Read, Update, Delete, Execute, downLoad).

We follow the EU recommendation “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”

A potential schema for managing authorisation is the one below. It needs to be discussed, but it should be simple enough to be applied to all RIs in ENVRI-FAIR in agreement with policies at WP4. Also we need to be aligned with GDPR.

#	Level	Required attributes	Requirements for user	Rights
0	untrusted (anonymous)	(none)	no email confirmation	just access metadata

1	normal user	user	email confirmation (not confirmed name)	access open resources (e.g services)
2	resource access (including workflows and sensor networks, TNA?)	user & access	trusted affiliation and name	access open resources and resources that require trusted users
3	access to embargoed resources	users & specific restricted access attribute (e.g. EPOS member)	trusted affiliation, name and user group	access to embargoed resources
4	processing	user & processing	trusted affiliation and user role	access to computational resources
5	admin	admin	manually added to admin group	

In general authorisation is achieved by using the authentication token and adding keys, where the keys express permissions to access assets.

Also in the authorisation case, different protocols have different procedures. Agreeing on one protocol makes - of course - the entire process much easier, as explained here <https://www.axiomatics.com/blog/authentication-vs-authorisation-part-2-saml-and-oauth-2/>

5.6. Policies

ENVRI-FAIR WP4 needs to define clearly policies covering AAAI. This includes security, privacy, trust which provide the policy framework for an implementation of AAAI. However, asset policies relating to data, data products, services, software and other assets are required and lead to specification of IT subsystems for curation and provenance (as well as access control by authentication and authorisation) which also link to AAAI in other ways.

The whole policy framework (and the IT implementation to support it) also needs to manage RRI (Responsible Research and Innovation) including e.g. ethics and non-discrimination and - of course - GDPR related to privacy of personal data.

A simplified policy overview related to AAAI and ENVRI IT activities is presented:

→ Suggestion to WP4 to keep policies simple (e.g. 2 level might be enough - admin and normal user)

The intention of the diagram is to show that policies concerning AAI depend on policies concerning persons, identity, authentication and permissions/rights (brown boxes left side of diagram) and policies concerning assets (golden boxes right side of diagram) with the two aspects mediated by the AAI components in the blue boxes in the middle of the diagram. With all these relationships/connections between the boxes it becomes clear that the more complex the policies, the more complex (by one or more orders of magnitude) becomes the implementation. Hence the exhortation to WP4 to keep policies as simple as possible (but as complicated as necessary).

6. Conclusions

WP TF2 has managed to do a large amount of work. However, there is much to be done. The major conclusions are:

1. ENVRI needs a set of policies, clearly defined, to provide the framework for AAI;
2. ENVRI needs to have an architecture (ENVRI-Hub) within which to implement those policies;
3. a solution for authentication that is generally acceptable to the RIs using OpenID (on top of OAuth2) is recommended;
4. more work is required to define a recommendation for authorisation. This is dependent on (a) ENVRI policies; (b) a landscape analysis of existing solutions in different RIs; (c) further work by TF2 to analyse (b) and plan a route to convergence on a recommendable solution which is likely to be OAuth2;
5. ENVRI needs to ensure that all RIs and the ENVRI-Hub have appropriate policies and mechanisms in place for AAI including for GDPR. These include (a) appropriate disclaimers (liability, terms and conditions, cookies) and informed

consent at the user interface; (b) security and privacy generally and related to access control (authorisation) (c) data subject access and processing;

6. The future work within TF2 should include a use case collection in order to better understand and capture all the specific requirements from the communities. This might in turn influence the architectural approach and inform better the group at all levels, from the policy to the technical implementation.

7. ANNEX I - How AAI is done now in each RI

AnaEE

AnaEE has introduced user identity federation at DMP level, expecting its adhering bodies to manage their users with Identity Management tools that implement the OpenID protocol for user identity and OAuth for user authorisation. With these standards AnaEE can implement decentralized AAI since OpenID compliant AAI providers can be linked to each other. This means that no user account data is transferred to the AnaEE ID provider, but rather that the AnaEE ID provider can peek into the adhering institution's one to verify the claims of a user. When an institution's ID provider is connected to an AnaEE ID provider, it becomes part of the network and the accounts therein contained are referred to "AnaEE accounts". For instance right now all CREA accounts are AnaEE accounts because CREA's identity provider has been linked to the ID provider hosted by AnaEE's Data & Modelling Centre. AnaEE expects this kind of federation to be regulated by an agreement where all the user data management implications of this account federation procedure are presented to the adhering institution.

AnaEE, however, does not force all of its potential users to register an AnaEE account and allows its adhering institution to run and manage their own private account systems for their services. By doing this AnaEE is not interfering with the existing (or future) business model and/or user account policies of adhering institutions, but rather providing them with an additional service to help increase their user base and traction.

At practical level, this decision implies that AnaEE services can be accessed by creating an account for each one of them, or by using an AnaEE account across all of them (much in the likes of "sign in with Google/Facebook/Whatever). This design is evident in the login page of AnaEE's developer portal, as shown below

Sign in

Not a member yet? [Sign up.](#)

Email

Password

Sign in

[Forgot your password?](#)

Sign in with AnaEE Account

If your institution is part of AnaEE, you can access our APIs with your institutional account with no need of registering new accounts.

[Sign in with AnaEE account](#)

The differences between logging in with a system-specific account and the AnaEE account consist mostly in account management: with AnaEE account you have one password to remember and your account is protected by a two factor authentication, moreover you will be able to track your sign-ins across different systems that accept AnaEE accounts, making it possible to detect unauthorized access and identity theft more easily.

Aside from that, at the current state, logging in with AnaEE does not grant additional privileges with respect to non-AnaEE users (if a user hierarchy exists in the system the AnaEE-logged user's privileges have to be elevated within the consumer application). In fact, first time log-in with an AnaEE account may result in the system requiring you data to fill in your profile, like setting up a regular account, since, by design, AnaEE expects very little

personal data (namely name, surname, institution, and email) to be shared through its ID provider. However, if an adhering platform would like a different policy to be implemented, AnaEE is able to provide authorisation tokens as well, so AnaEE users would be able to access additional services without having to let their personal data transit on the platform's system.

SIOS

SIOS web portal is based on Drupal 7 (soon Drupal 8) which supports basic authentication and authorisation with creations of custom accounts on the server, and potential creation of additional roles. Currently we only have 2 types of roles, i.e. administrator and authenticated users.

Authenticated users can have additional intranet roles to access specific internal documentation, e.g. working group minutes and drafts.

Data search and discovery is open and freely accessible by anonymous users as well as full data download through links to the contributing data centers. Remote streaming of data through OPeNDAP, when available, as well as data visualization is open to anonymous users.

Only one service within SIOS requires authentication, i.e. a basket service for subsetting of data. All authenticated users have access to this service without any further restrictions.

EPOS

Introduction

In the framework of EPOS, a general agreement within WP6/7 was reached about the fact that management of AAAI should be handled by specialised institutions both for technical and governance reasons. For technical reasons, because in EPOS one of the main requirements is to be able to support and integrate several Authentication Systems, for governance reasons because AAAI management also requires to cope with administrative matters (i.e. identifying users and dealing with authorisations) which specialised institutions are already prepared to face.

The AAI hosting institution should be indeed able to provide:

8. IT authentication: the authentication that the user is the person (in role user) that they say they are; this can be done whether integrating existing AAI IdP or by providing registration features;
9. EPOS stakeholder authorisation management: it prescribes that EPOS organisation managers should be able to apply specific authorisation schemes to existing users in point (1), so that EPOS “knows” what users are entitled to use what resources.

AAI technical architecture

In the proposed architecture, AAI is managed by an external EPOS component. This component has the following features:

- it can register new users
- it can integrate existing users from other IdP (e.g. Edugain)
- it enables EPOS managers to assign specific authorisation to specific users
- when users are redirected from the GUI to the AAI component, the AAI component issues a token so that the GUI can act on behalf of the user
- it accepts connection by proxies at ICS and TCS level, that will check that the token is still valid, that the user has appropriate authorisation, session has not expired etc.

In the figure above the architecture of components in the EPOS system are presented. The architecture is a kind of micro service approach where the system integrated many existing services. Many of them are developed especially to build the EPOS system but others are the legacy services that need to be integrated (TCS services and e-infrastructure/HPC services). Therefore, the main challenge is implementing authentication and authorisation into the EPOS system that provides a solution for chains of API/web services calls. The relevant standard for this OAuth2 Token Exchange (in mature draft <https://tools.ietf.org/html/draft-ietf-oauth-token-exchange-15>). This standard structure the tokens and mechanism to obtain and to validate them in Authentication Service. EPOS was validating this solution. It appeared that for legacy services and for wider adoption of solution creating an authentication proxy, this is a LUA module in web server, would be a helpful solution.

The general assumption is that the context of an authenticated user is transferred to the underlying web services using *tokens*. The important feature is that tokens can be added to a HTTP call without interfering with the semantics of the services itself. They are added as authentication mechanism additional field in the header. Like here:

```
authorisation: Bearer TOKEN
```

EPOS AAI prototypes that are based on UNITY-IDM have already an implementation of the OAuth2 Token Exchange mechanism, so the prototype was deployed to support a delegation scenario.

Options for login/register

EPOS AAI service will be organized in the distributed fashion based on good practices and standards in the field. EPOS would like to take advantage of value gained by existing authentication infrastructures and services. Therefore the planned options to register/login includes:

- EGI CheckIn -- collects various accounts (including EduGAIN accounts) and provide growing set of trusted attributes (like important institution affiliation or country),
- TCS existing login (IDPs, LDAP if supported) -- to keep possibility of existing TCS users to use EPOS services,
- on site registration -- for user that does not have any organisational account integrated, this require additional procedures to confirm email and required attributes, for users that want to register with social accounts email confirmation is not necessary.

Every method of registering will require completing a *user profile* with the required attributes. In case a method of authentication supports some of the user profile elements, the require attributes must be collected from user at the registration stage.

Example of integrated authentication in EPOS

User profile

- first name
- last name(s)
- email (confirmation)
- affiliation

- can be confirmed by EduGAIN
- researcher status (?)
 - default NO
- EPOS member
 - manually managed with some EPOS authority?
- special EPOS member groups membership

Level	Required attributes	Requirements for user
untrusted	(none)	no email confirmation
normal user	user	email confirmation (not confirmed name)
data access	user & access	trusted affiliation
processing	user & processing	
admin	admin	manually added to admin group

Authentication for Web Services (WS)

All EPOS services will work according to a delegation scheme based on OAuth2. The token will be added to each request from the GUI to any EPOS service including ICS-C components and TCS WSs.

TCS WS Authentication

- Providers may implement authentication and authorisation based on OAuth2 token and EPOS AAI services.
- For legacy systems the provider may use NGINX “proxy” which executes validity of token and selected attributes

GDPR

AAI service will be the main point of accepting data usage policies informed by the metadata catalog. AAI provider and ICS provider will guarantee compliance with GDPR. Details need to be designed and additional effort for implementing need to be allocated.

Ingesting personal data into EPOS catalogue

In order to enable the ICS system to manage user authorisation, the authorisation information can be passed from the AAI node to the EPOS CERIF catalogue through the token, which should include authorisation metadata.

Authorisation metadata can be of different kinds according to the IdP that was used to authenticate the user, so at some point in the communication between AAI node and EPOS catalogue, an authorisation metadata mapping procedure is envisaged.

For instance, this mapping procedure might establish that all users from “social accounts” have no rights of downloading datasets but only access to metadata, and that all users from official IdP (like Edugain) are entitled *at least* to download both metadata and datasets.

EMSO ERIC

Introduction

The European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water-column Observatory (EMSO) aims to explore the oceans and explain the driving factors and the effects of changes in the broader earth systems, focusing on climate change, warning signals of biodiversity loss and ecosystem impact, and geo-hazards. A fundamental component of the EMSO cyber-infrastructure that integrates multiple ocean variables from EMSO regional facilities is its data management platform.

EMSO engaged with European Grid Infrastructure (EGI) to develop an initial data management platform as part of the EMSODEV H2020 project. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Early Adopters Programme supports the transition of the EMSO data management platform to pre-production and provides critical components within the EOSC-hub project and its partners for the deployment of EMSO ERIC data services, including the EMSO ERIC Authentication and authorisation Infrastructure (AAI). This transition enables data and services to be harmonized and standardized across EMSO observatories. It also increases its interoperability with the marine subdomain according to FAIR principles as part of the ENVRI-FAIR H2020 project, which will ultimately deliver EMSO ERIC added value data services via the EOSC marketplace impacting different communities.

emso
ERIC

EMSO-ERIC LOGIN

Sign in

Username or email

Password

Remember me [Forgot Password?](#)

Sign In

Or sign in with

EGI Check-in

G **Google**

New user? [Register](#)

EOSC-Hub currently provides cloud-based resources from two geo-distributed datacenters and critical services, such as support for integrating the Authentication and authorisation Infrastructure using the EGI Check-in service.

The EMSO ERIC AAI's current implementation is focused on authentication and authorisation and does not consider accounting for now.

AAI technical architecture

The EMSO ERIC regional facilities typically provide data following an open-access approach; however, access to data services that may be resource-demanding requires authentication to share resources effectively. Furthermore, heavy-resource consuming services such as the EMSO ERIC virtual research environment or specialized dashboards require authorisation. As a result, the authentication and authorisation infrastructure is used for advanced features while not required for basic features.

Different design choices were studied with the goal of providing a flexible and low-maintenance cost solution, including the EGI check-in service. While this service allows federating different identify providers, including the EMSO ERIC identity provider, EMSO ERIC has adopted the AARC blueprint architecture for flexibility (e.g., a user can choose the preferred identity provider) and enabling the federation within ENVRI-FAIR.

The overarching architecture of the EMSO ERIC AAI is illustrated in the figure below.

AAI Integration with data services

The implemented AAI solution is used in employing the single sign-on scheme in accessing different EMSO ERIC data services without re-entering authentication.

Key services include:

- The EMSO ERIC data management platform API, a RESTful web service tool, allows programmatic access to EMSO ERIC data within its data management platform. Users or third-party repositories can use it via machine-to-machine interfaces. In addition to facilitating data discovery, access, and download, it enables building tools, including data portals, dashboards for data visualization, data product generation, etc. The current implementation based on the Swagger open-source framework provides a set of basic endpoints (or operations) and uses authentication for a subset of functions and administrative operations.
- The EMSO ERIC data portal provides access to EMSO ERIC data with a focus on essential ocean variables. It provides open access to a description of the different observatories, pointers to existing data and meta-data sources, and an overview of visualizations. The data portal also serves as the interface for users to request access to advanced features such as a virtual research environment based on Jupyter.

8. ANNEX 2 USEFUL MATERIAL

Authentication:

<https://www.axiomatics.com/blog/authentication-vs-authorization-part-2-saml-and-oauth-2/>

Authorisation: Different protocols have different procedures. Agreeing on one protocol makes of course the entire process much easier.

<https://www.axiomatics.com/blog/authentication-vs-authorisation-part-2-saml-and-oauth-2/>

GDPR: <https://www.gdpr.eu>

EPOS on AAI (working document)

https://docs.google.com/document/d/15O3Hez9A-THSiOLq6asELyihJqfNjgQ_CycrTBXZqfk/edit#

AAI in Elixir (as an example of another RI) <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

9. ANNEX 3 - AAI

The following solutions are compatible with the suggested protocols and with each other:

- Azure Active Directory
- AuthAnvil Single Sign On 4.5
- BIG-IP with Access Policy Manager
- BitGlass
- CA Secure Cloud
- CA SiteMinder 12.52
- Centrify
- Citrix
- Dell One Identity Cloud Access Manager v7.1
- DigitalPersona Composite Authentication
- ForgeRock Identity Platform Access Management V5.x
- IBM Tivoli Federated Identity Manager 6.2.2
- IceWall Federation Version 3.0
- Keycloak
- Memory
- NetIQ Access Manager 4.x
- Okta
- OneLogin
- Optimal IDM Virtual Identity Server Federation Services
- PingFederate 6.11, 7.2, 8.x
- RadiantOne CFS 3.0
- Sailpoint IdentityNow
- SecureAuth IdP 7.2.0
- Sign&go 5.3
- SoftBank Technology Online Service Gate
- VMware Workspace One